

The effect of perfluorosulfonic acid membrane molecular structure on excessive swelling in the context of PEM water electrolysis at elevated temperature and pressure

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Abstract

Increasing the operating temperature and pressure of proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEM WE) enhances energy efficiency at high hydrogen production rates, but membrane stability is a limiting factor in this approach. Excessive water uptake (excessive swelling) is an often-overlooked phenomenon in PEM water electrolysis field, despite its significant impact on membrane properties and system performance. In this study, four commercial PEMs were selected to investigate effects of side chain length and equivalent weight on their excessive swelling. Membrane samples were exposed to liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa for 800 hours, while in-plane resistivity was continuously monitored. All membranes showed a gradual increase in resistivity over time. Before and after the hydrothermal treatment, the membranes were characterized using small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and atomic force microscopy (AFM). The results show that swelling is mainly governed by membrane hydrophilicity and that, unlike previous reports, exceeding the α -transition temperature is not required for excessive swelling to occur. Long side chains were associated with a lesser degree of resistivity increase, which was connected to larger hydrophilic domains that likely promote a more favourable mesoscale morphology at very high water contents. Our study showed that while excessive water uptake at elevated temperature and pressure represents serious stability issues. Careful design of the membrane's internal morphology might help mitigate these undesirable effects.

Graphical Abstract

PFSA membranes in **LIQUID** water at 120 °C and 600 kPa for 800 hours

Key words

PFSA membranes, PEM water electrolysis, excessive swelling, proton conductivity

Highlights

- PFSA membranes were exposed to liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa for 800 h
- Excessive water uptake leads to conductance and crystallinity loss
- Equivalent weight (hydrophilicity) determines the severity of degradation
- Side-chain length influences hydrophilic domains size and tortuosity
- Short side chains result in negligible amount of bulk-like water in the membrane

1. Introduction

To address climate change, the European Union has set an ambitious target to achieve greenhouse gas neutrality by 2050 [1]. Hydrogen is anticipated to play a pivotal role in the transformation of the energy system due to its wide range of applications. It can serve as a feedstock chemical in industrial production, be utilised for industrial heating, iron production, as a fuel in the transport sector, or it can act as an energy carrier in renewable power generation [2]. Proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEM WE) represents one of the key electrochemical technologies for hydrogen production in this scheme.

PEM WE offers several advantages. Compared to other technologies available for water splitting, it allows flexible changes in hydrogen production rate from nearly shutdown to high current density (around 2 A cm⁻² in commercial electrolyzers [3]). The relative compactness of the PEM electrolyzers allows for a small site footprint, and when operated at optimum conditions, PEM electrolyzers produce hydrogen of high purity with high energy efficiency. However, the need for corrosion-resistant titanium components and precious group metal (PGM) catalysts and coatings drives up the investment costs of electrolyzers. Therefore, to improve the economic viability of the PEM WE technology, it is essential to further intensify hydrogen production in PEM water electrolyzers while ensuring their long-term stability. One potential approach of PEM water electrolysis intensification is increasing the operating

temperature and pressure. This would improve energy efficiency by lowering the equilibrium voltage and, more importantly, by enhancing reaction kinetics, and proton conductivity of the membrane electrolyte. Increased pressure also improves mass transfer on the anode, enabling reaching higher current densities without reaching performance limitations.

PEM water electrolyzers typically operate at temperatures around 60 – 90°C. Raising the operational temperature can introduce material stability challenges. Particularly, at temperatures above the boiling point of water (steam electrolysis), membrane drying becomes a significant issue [4]. In this regard, researchers have explored solutions such as use of composite membrane electrolytes with hydrophilic fillers, alternative membrane chemistries like doped polybenzimidazole, or phosphoric acid doping of conventional membranes based on perfluorinated sulfonic acid (PFSA) [5-8]. However, these approaches failed to provide competitive performance and stability.

Another approach to prevent membrane drying is to pressurise the electrolyser, maintaining water in its liquid state. However, experimental reports on the operation of PEM WE at elevated temperatures and pressures remain limited, and long-term performance and stability data are lacking. Existing studies have primarily used Nafion membranes as the electrolyte, exploring operational temperatures between 60 °C and 120 °C under pressures of 3 to 5 bar [9-12]. While operation at elevated temperature and pressure overall improves the energy efficiency, it also leads to an increase in hydrogen crossover [9, 10]. Moreover, higher temperatures place additional stress on PFSA membranes, leading to accelerated membrane thinning and higher fluoride release rates [10, 13]. Studies at elevated temperatures and pressures have also been conducted using composite membranes. In these studies, hydrophilic fillers such as TiO₂ or SiO₂ in Nafion matrix have been shown to be beneficial for the electrolyser performance at temperatures of up to 120 °C and pressure of 3 bar [14-16]. Similarly, composites of polysulfone nanofibers and Aquivion have been demonstrated to improve performance and to reduce gas crossover between electrode compartments [17].

As mentioned, degradation mechanisms, such as membrane thinning and chemical degradation, are often taken into consideration in PEM WE studies. However, the phenomenon of excessive swelling during prolonged operation (especially at elevated temperature and pressure) remains relatively underexplored, despite its significant impact on membrane performance. Moreover, PFSA membrane research is still predominantly focused on their application in PEM fuel cells, most of the available data on water sorption in membranes is focused on absorption of water vapour. Yet, it is the understanding of the long-term behaviour of PFSA membranes in liquid water, which is crucial for improving the durability and reliability of PEM water electrolyzers.

The water sorption behaviour of PFSA membranes plays a fundamental role in defining their morphological, mechanical, and transport properties. Upon hydration, PFSA membranes exhibit phase separation due to their amphiphilic nature: the hydrophobic polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) backbone forms a mechanically robust matrix, while the sulfonic acid ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) side chains interact with water molecules to form hydrophilic domains through solvation [18]. The mechanical stability of the hydrated PFSA membranes is given by the balance between the internal pressure exerted by absorbed water and the resistance of the polymer matrix to deformation [18]. The hydrated domains, once sufficiently connected, create percolating networks that enable proton conduction. The mesoscale arrangement of these hydrophilic domains (including their size, connectivity, and spatial distribution) is a key factor in the ion transport and overall membrane performance [18]. This morphology arises from the interplay of polymer solvation, nanophase separation, and the molecular structure of the PFSA polymer. Moreover, the degree of crystallinity in the hydrophobic matrix, governed by the length of the polymer backbone between side chains, enhances mechanical stability by forming crystalline regions that resist swelling-induced deformation [18]. However, increasing backbone length and crystallinity often comes at the cost of reducing the density of sulfonic acid groups, thereby lowering ionic conductivity [18]. Thus, a trade-off exists between optimizing mechanical integrity and ensuring sufficient charge carrier density. While presence of certain amount of water in the PFSA membrane is necessary in order to establish the ion-conducting two-phase structure, extensive amount of water leads to deterioration of its physico-chemical and mechanical properties [19-21].

The water absorption is temperature dependent. When immersed in liquid water (or exposed to water vapour of high enough activity), increasing temperature leads to an increase of water absorption by the polymer [18, 22]. A crucial point on the temperature scale regarding PFSA membrane excessive swelling has been identified by Mališ et al [19, 20]. In these studies, it was shown that (protonated) Nafion 117 membrane immersed in liquid water at temperatures above approx. 110 °C and at increased pressure (500 and 700 kPa) rapidly loses its ionic conductivity and mechanical stability. No chemical changes (IR, NMR) were identified, and this degradation was ascribed to excessive swelling accompanied with changes of the membrane internal structure and crystallinity decrease. The temperature of 110 °C roughly coincides with the α -transition of Nafion (corresponding to a destabilization of the electrostatic network that facilitates long-range polymer mobility [23, 24]) and the observed behaviour was therefore linked to this transition.

Most insights into the α -transition of PFSA membranes come from dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of dry samples, where Nafion shows a sharp drop in elastic modulus near its α -transition temperature [24, 25]. However, even moderate humidity ($\text{RH} > 15\%$) suppresses this mechanical signature, highlighting that hydration significantly alters membrane behaviour [22, 26, 27]. Although hydrated

PFSA membranes show no clear mechanical response at the α -transition temperature, dielectric spectroscopy (DS) reveals that α -relaxation still occurs and is linked to longitudinal polarization of rod-like polymer aggregates [28-30]. DS studies on humidified Nafion (RH > 60 %) identified a transition near 120 °C (or ~80 °C for membranes with lower equivalent weight), marked by a frequency shift of both α and β relaxations which was attributed to a conformational change driven by electrostatic repulsion between dissociated $-\text{SO}_3^-$ groups. As the conformation change increases molecular rigidity, it likely accounts for the suppressed viscoelastic signature seen in DMA under humid conditions. In hydrated membranes at temperatures above the α -transition temperature, this conformational change likely enhances water absorption, as observed by Mališ et al [19, 20] and other authors [22, 31].

In comparison to Nafion, Aquivion membranes feature shorter side chains. This design of chemical structure allows for higher crystallinity, improved mechanical properties and a higher α -transition temperature [32]. Therefore, Aquivion membranes may represent a more suitable option for application in PEM WE at elevated temperature and pressure compared to long-side-chained Nafions. In their comprehensive study, Moukheiber et al. [32] reported that the α -transition temperature of Aquivions (E79, E83, E87, E91, E110) reach values between 120 and 140 °C (based on their equivalent weight), while in case of Nafion (211, 111), it is around 100 °C. However, it is important to mention, that the values of α -transition temperature found for Nafion across different studies are not very consistent. In particular, the values available in the literature for Nafion 111, 117, 1035, 1110 vary between 60 °C and 115 °C (in all cases, the polymers have equivalent weight of 1100 g mol⁻¹ [18, 27, 32-34]).

The main aim of this study is to get closer insight on the relation between molecular structure of commercial PFSA membranes and their sensitivity to excessive swelling. This will help to select optimal materials for desired application. In order to achieve this target, the excessive swelling of PFSA membranes in liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa was followed with respect to their side-chain structure and equivalent weight. In particular, four different PFSA membranes were enclosed in a pressurised and heated conductivity cell with circulating water. Here, their membrane ionic conductivity was monitored in the course of 800 h long experiment. The membranes were then thoroughly characterised with various techniques to determine their morphology and physico-chemical changes induced by this hydrothermal treatment.

2. Experimental Methods

2.1 Chemicals

Deionised water used in the experiments was produced using a DIWA 3rica (Watek) reverse osmosis module, with a conductivity of freshly deionised water of 0.5 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. The following chemicals were

used for the preparation of solutions described in the next section (all analytical grade purity): H₂O₂ (30 wt.%, Lachner), H₂SO₄ (96 wt.%, Lachner), NaCl (solid, Penta), HCl (standard solution, Normalal Lachema), and NaOH (50 wt.% solution, Acros Organics).

2.2 Hydrothermal treatment with ionic conductivity measurement

Four different commercially available PFSA membranes subjected to an environment of elevated temperature and pressure are summarised in **Table 1**. This selection of membranes was intended to cover a range of molecular structure parameters that influence membrane properties. The chosen membranes include those with long side chains (**N117** and **F940**) and those with short side chains (**AQE98** and **AQE87**). Side chain length is a critical factor, as it significantly impacts the α -transition temperature. Additionally, **AQE98** and **AQE87** were selected to investigate the effect of equivalent weight, which influences both the α -transition temperature and polymer hydrophilicity. The effect of membrane reinforcement will also be explored, using the **F940** membrane as an example. **F940** is solvent-cast, unlike the other membranes, which are produced by melt extrusion.

As the very first step, the membranes were activated and cleaned according to established procedure [19]. The as-received membranes were immersed in 80 °C deionized (DI) water for 60 min, then in 3 wt.% H₂O₂ solution heated to 60 °C for 30 min and in 0.05 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution at 60 °C for 30 min. As the final step of the activation, the membranes were immersed in pure DI water at 60 °C for 120 min. During all steps, the solutions were gently stirred with magnetic stirring bar.

Table 1 – Overview of studied membranes with their specifications; t stands for thickness, EW denotes equivalent weight, LSC and SSC denote long-side-chained and short-side-chained membranes, respectively

Membrane	Abbreviation	Manufacturer	t_{dry} / μm	t_{swollen} / μm	EW / g per SO ₃ ⁻	Features
Nafion N117	N117	Chemours	183	210	1100	LSC, extruded
Fumapem F-940-RF	F940	Fumatech	40	70	870	LSC, reinforced, cast
Aquivion E87-05S	AQE87	Solvay	50	76	870	SSC, extruded
Aquivion E98-05S	AQE98	Solvay	50	66	980	SSC, extruded

For the ionic conductivity measurement, the activated membrane samples (1 cm × 6 cm) were enclosed in a conductivity cell and contacted with four Pt wires in a row (four-electrode arrangement) with distance between two (inner) sensing electrodes and (outer) feeding electrodes being 4 and 5.4 cm, respectively. Each half of the made-in-house cell featured a 1 cm × 6 cm × 1 mm groove to accommodate the membrane and allow the DI water to flow around the membrane. The cell was closed

and tightened by eight M8 bolts using 5 N m torque. After assembly, the cell was placed inside an oven and connected to a hydraulic circuit with circulating DI water ($0.5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$), for schematic of the setup, see **Figure S1** in Supporting Information file. The cell inside the oven was heated to $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the circulating water was pressurised to 500 kPa of overpressure (to ensure the water stays liquid); the system remained at these conditions for 800 h. To avoid membrane contamination by metal ions the hydraulic circuit was equipped with an ion-exchange mixed bed resin column and all circuit components (except for metallic back-pressure regulators) were made of plastic. In particular, perfluoroalkoxy (Swagelok®) tubing, polyetheretherketone (PEEK) cell body and polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) sealings were used. Throughout this hydrothermal treatment, the in-plane ohmic resistance (R_Ω) of the membrane was continuously monitored by means of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using an LCR bridge H8118 (Rohde & Schwarz). The impedance spectra were measured at an open circuit potential using 100 mV amplitude and 200 kHz to 20 Hz frequency range. From the obtained spectra (example spectra can be found in **Figure S2**), ohmic resistance R_Ω was evaluated as the real part of impedance of experimental point closest to the x axis in the Nyquist diagram in the high frequency part of the spectrum using a Python-based algorithm.

2.3 Post mortem physico-chemical characterisation of membranes

Ion-exchange capacity (IEC) was evaluated by acid-base titration using an automatic potentiostatic titrator (HI 932, Hanna Instruments). All solutions were prepared from DI water. First, a small piece of the membrane ($1.5 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm}$) was dropped inside 60 mL of N_2 -purged 0.1 mol dm^{-3} NaCl solution where H^+ ions in the membrane were exchanged for Na^+ ions. After stabilisation of pH (around 5 min), the solution with the membrane sample was titrated with approx. 0.01 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution. The exact concentration of the NaOH solution was determined by titration using a standard 0.05 mol dm^{-3} solution of HCl. After the titration, the membrane samples (in Na^+ form) were removed, rinsed in DI water, and converted back to the H^+ form by 30 min immersion in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} HCl followed by careful rinsing in DI water (first under flowing water and then the samples were left over night in around 50 cm^3 of DI water). These re-protonated (RP) membranes were again titrated with NaOH solution following the same procedure. After the second titration, the membranes were re-protonated again, tapped with a paper cloth to remove droplets on their surface and weighted (MS304TS, Mettler Toledo). Finally, the membranes were dried (10 min, $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air environment) and weighted again. Water content was determined from mass of the samples before and after drying.

The internal structure of the membranes was investigated using Small and Wide-angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS and WAXS). The experiments were performed using a pinhole camera (modified molecular metrology system; Rigaku, Japan) attached to a microfocused X-ray beam generator (Rigaku MicroMax

003) operated at 50 kV and 0.6 mA (30 W). The camera was equipped with a vacuum compatible version of Pilatus3 R 300 K hybrid photon-counting detector. A setup upgrade made by SAXSLAB enabled the detector to stay aligned with the beam. Three different sample-to-detector distances – 50, 400, and 1 400 mm were used to cover a wider q -range. The exposure time used was 4 hours. The scattering vector, q , is defined by **Eq. (Error! Reference source not found.)**, where $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$ is the radiation wavelength and 2θ is the scattering angle. Measured diffractograms were fitted according to a procedure described in detail in Section S2 of the SI file.

$$q = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta) \quad (1)$$

Scanning probe microscope Dimension ICON PT (Bruker) was used for observation of the samples in Peak Force Quantitative Mechanical Property Mapping (PF QNM) mode. The observation provides the topography of the surface depicted as a height image, local elastic properties of the sample as DMT modulus and local adhesivity of the sample. Bruker silicon nitride probes Scanasyt-air were utilised with tip apex diameter of 2 to 3 nm and the spring constant $k = 0.4 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ during measurement of as-received samples. Bruker silicon nitride probes Scanasyt-fluid+ with tip apex diameter of 2 to 4 nm and the spring constant $k = 0.7 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ were utilised for measurement of wet samples (activated and treated membranes). No damage of samples caused by the scanning probe was observed for the as-received and activated membranes. Each sample was examined on both sides. Each side was examined at two or three spots. Range of scan sizes: 10 μm , 3 μm , 1 μm , 350 nm. The resulting images were evaluated by NanoScope Analysis 1.50 software. Selected topographical images were processed with a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis with stopband filter 55 nm to increase their clarity.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to investigate the state of water in the samples. Prior to insertion of the samples inside the calorimeter, the wet membrane samples were placed in an open aluminium pan and were put in a concealed containers containing solutions of NaCl (10 mg cm^{-3}) for a duration of one week in order to equilibrate the samples with water vapour at room temperature. After that, the aluminium pans were hermetically sealed. For the measurement, Q2000 differential scanning calorimeter was used. The procedure was performed in an inert atmosphere of N_2 with a gas flow rate of 50 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The measurements were carried out in cooling - heating regime, i.e. from +20 to $-70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and back to +20 $^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature change rate was 10 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Data were evaluated from cooling and heating curves using TA Instruments Trios software. The samples were then dried at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h. Water content for DSC-measured samples was established from their weights before and after drying.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Hydrothermal treatment and conductivity monitoring

Activated membranes were exposed to 800 h hydrothermal treatment in liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa, during which the conductivity cell with the membrane sample was continuously monitored by EIS, allowing to evaluate the time evolution of the ohmic resistance, R_{Ω} . As shown in **Figure 1**, starting from about 1 k Ω , R_{Ω} gradually increased for all tested membranes. The most significant increase occurred in the cell containing the reinforced membrane (**F940**), where R_{Ω} rapidly reached several hundreds of k Ω . This suggests practically complete loss of ionic conductivity of the membrane. In contrast, the remaining membranes showed more stable performance. In particular, the least pronounced R_{Ω} change was shown by cell with **AQE98**, which exhibited a 13 % increase in R_{Ω} , followed by **N117** with a 19 % R_{Ω} increase and **AQE87** with R_{Ω} increase of 58 %. Notably, the rate of R_{Ω} increase varies over time and differs between membranes. For **N117** and both Aquivion membranes (**AQE87** and **AQE98**), the most pronounced rise in R_{Ω} is observed during the first 200 h of the hydrothermal treatment and then slows down. After the initial 200 h period, the **AQE87** membrane shows a steady R_{Ω} increase with a slope $dR_{\Omega}/dt \approx 0.4 \Omega h^{-1}$. On the other hand, **N117** demonstrated the slowest R_{Ω} increase with $dR_{\Omega}/dt \approx 0.03 \Omega h^{-1}$. Therefore, from a long-term perspective, **N117** seems to be the most stable among the studied membranes.

Figure 1 – Time evolution of the R_{Ω} of the conductivity cell with the membrane samples enclosed in it at 120 °C and 600 kPa. Each line represents a separate measurement. ΔR_{Ω} demotes the ohmic resistance change over 800 h while the time derivative dR_{Ω}/dt corresponds to the average slope of a linear regressions fitted to the curves for times above 200 h.

After cooling and removal from the conductivity cell, the membranes were further analysed. It is clear that the state of the membrane at ambient temperature and pressure differs from that during hydrothermal treatment. However, at least part of the structural changes is clearly preserved. The first inspection after the hydrothermal treatment revealed complete collapse (loss of mechanical integrity and volume) of the **F940** membrane. A significant portion of the ionomer from the **F940** membrane appeared to delaminate from the reinforcing mesh, and it was flushed out of the cell by the circulating water, which explains the dramatic increase in R_{Ω} . The extruded membranes (**N117**, **AQE87**, **AQE98**) became wrinkled (illustrative photos in **Figure S3**) and fragile. The prominent wrinkling of the extruded membranes was very probably caused by membrane swelling while being constricted inside the conductivity cell.

The complete mechanical failure of the **F940** membrane is likely related to differences in its fabrication process. Although literature sources do not suggest that solvent casting inherently produces unstable membranes [18, 35, 36], the resulting quality strongly depends on fabrication parameters such as the choice of solvent, casting temperature, and post-treatment conditions [37, 38]. Since the exact manufacturing procedure of the commercial membranes is confidential, the specific reason for the observed failure can only be speculated. It should be noted that the **F940** membrane was primarily developed for PEM fuel cell applications, where it would not be exposed to such extreme conditions.

Evaluated dimensional and volumetric changes in the membranes are presented in **Table 2**. However, due to their increased fragility and irregular shape, precise measurement of their dimensions was difficult (estimated error in length determination is about 20 %, thickness and width about 10 %), and quantitative value on these numbers is limited. It can be noticed that all membranes swell anisotropically – both Aquivions showed the most pronounced change in their thickness, whereas **N117** exhibited the most noticeable change in length. Overall, **AQE98** proved to be the most dimensionally stable of investigated membranes under the experimental conditions.

Table 2 – Changes in dimensions of membrane samples after the thermal treatment at 120 °C and 600 kPa for duration of 800 hrs. The abbreviations denote following parameters: t = thickness, w = width, L = length, V = volume.

Membrane	$\Delta t / \%$	$\Delta w / \%$	$\Delta L / \%$	$\Delta V / \%$
N117	+47	+19	+100	+250
AQE87	+133	+26	+33	+292
AQE98	+68	+12	+26	+137

Through **Eq. (1)** the measured dimensions were also used to calculate membrane resistivity at both the beginning and end of the experiment. The symbols t , w and L in **Eq. (1)** correspond to membrane

thickness, width and length, respectively. These calculations were based on the R_{Ω} values. While absolute values R_{Ω} include minor contributions from the wires and contacts in the whole experimental setup, the majority of changes in R_{Ω} can be attributed to the resistance within the membrane (and its contact to the sensing electrodes). As shown in **Table 3**, **AQE87** exhibited significant changes in material properties, resulting in a 247 % increase in resistivity. Interestingly, resistivity of **N117** increased by only 7 %.

$$\rho = \frac{R_{\Omega} \cdot t \cdot w}{L} \quad (1)$$

Table 3 – Resistivity values of the membranes at the start of the experiment at 120 °C and 600 kPa (the value of resistance used for the calculation includes contribution from the conductivity cell).

Membrane	ρ at $t = 0$ h at 120 °C / m Ω m	ρ at $t = 800$ h at 120 °C / m Ω m	$\Delta \rho$ / %
N117	23 ± 1	24 ± 1	+7
F940	33 ± 2	-	-
AQE87	19 ± 1	66 ± 4	+247
AQE98	15 ± 1	25 ± 2	+68

3.2 Ion-exchange capacity and water content determination

To provide a basic understanding of the observed phenomena and to elucidate the origin of the observed changes in the hydrothermally treated membranes, an ion-exchange capacity (IEC) of the membranes before and after the treatment was determined based on acid-base titration (with NaOH). After the titration, the membrane samples were re-protonated (RP), i.e. converted back to the H⁺-form, in HCl to remove any metal ions from their structure. Subsequently, the IEC of RP membranes was determined again. The results are summarised in **Figure 2a**. The difference in IEC between "activated" (samples before the hydrothermal treatment) and "treated" membranes, observed in all four samples, may suggest a loss of -SO₃H groups available for ion exchange. However, for the extruded membranes (**N117**, **AQE87** and **AQE98**), this diminished IEC was fully recovered through re-protonation. This reversible loss of IEC suggests potential foreign ion contamination of membranes during the hydrothermal treatment, likely due to residual ions from the circulating DI water or metallic back-pressure regulators. Most importantly, these results indicate that the changes in the internal membrane morphology (induced by the hydrothermal treatment) did not influence the amount of accessible -SO₃H groups as suggested previously [19, 20]. That is, there is no alteration in membrane morphology that would result in a more/less open structure leading to an increase/decrease in the IEC. In the case of the hydrothermally treated **F940** membrane, the pronounced decrease of IEC values clearly corresponds to the significant loss of ionomer during the experiment.

Figure 2 – a) Ion-exchange capacity values of activated membranes, thermally treated membranes and their re-protonated versions; b) water content in activated and treated membranes (drying at 90 °C for 10 min). Values represent the arithmetic mean obtained from analyses of two membrane samples. RP denotes “reprotonated”.

As mentioned above, IEC results suggested that membranes during hydrothermal treatment become partially contaminated by foreign cations, which could be a reason for the observed increase in membrane resistivity. To confirm or exclude this hypothesis, another sample of **AQE87** membrane (exhibiting the most pronounced IEC drop after the treatment, i.e. potentially highest level of contamination by foreign ions during the experiment) was exposed to hydrothermal treatment for 800 h. Then, the resistance of this membrane in the conductivity cell was measured by EIS at room temperature. After that, the sample was removed from the cell, re-protonated, inserted back in the cell and its resistance at room temperature was measured again. Since the re-protonation did not lead to a measurable decrease in R_{Ω} , it was concluded that foreign ion contamination was not the cause of the R_{Ω} changes observed during the hydrothermal treatment (results presented in **Figure S4**).

Important insights were gained by assessing the water content in the membranes. It was determined by comparing mass of the membrane samples measured before and after drying (at 90 °C for 10 min). As shown in **Figure 2b**, the hydrothermal treatment significantly increased the water content in all samples. **AQE98** ($\text{EW} = 980 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) showed lower affinity towards water than **AQE87** ($\text{EW} = 870 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), which is in agreement with expectation based on EW value. On the other hand, **N117** displayed relatively high water uptake despite its higher equivalent weight ($\text{EW} = 1100 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$). Due to differences in side chain length, direct comparison between **N117** and the Aquivion membranes based solely on EW is not straightforward. A much more suitable approach for comparison in this context is to subtract the molecular mass of the side chain from that of the monomer unit and calculate a new “equivalent weight” corresponding to the molecular mass of the backbone per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. From this value, the most illustrative step is to determine the number of tetrafluoroethylene (TFE) units in the repeating unit—in other words, the length of the backbone between the side chains. The polymer hydrophilicity then decreases with increasing length of the PTFE backbone between side chains (more TFE units). The

number of TFE units per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group is 7.0 for **AQE98**, 6.7 for **N117** and 5.9 for **AQE87**, indicating that **AQE98** should be the least hydrophilic, followed by **N117**, while **AQE87** should be the most hydrophilic. The number of TFE units also reflects the membrane's tendency to crystallize. More crystalline polymers typically absorb less water due to a stiffer matrix that restricts swelling. Based solely on the backbone structure, **N117** would not be expected to absorb significantly more water than **AQE98**. However, a clear difference was observed: **N117** absorbed about 63 % water, compared to 48 % for **AQE98** and 80 % for **AQE87**. This somewhat unexpectedly high water uptake by **N117** may result from its long side chains, reduced crystallinity, or other structural factors.

In any case, the increase in water content correlates positively with the rise in R_Ω observed during hydrothermal treatment. The relative change in R_Ω follows the sequence: **AQE87** > **N117** > **AQE98**, which mirrors the trends in water uptake and relative volume change (**Table 2**). This indicates that the change in cell R_Ω is primarily driven by water absorption. While part of the R_Ω increase results from membrane volume change rather than a decrease in its intrinsic ionic conductivity (as shown in **Table 3**), it is the effective R_Ω change that ultimately matters for practical applications.

At this point, it is appropriate to revisit the role of the α -transition temperature, which, as noted in the introduction, is shown to strongly influence swelling. All three investigated membranes exhibit excessive water absorption, with the extent decreasing in the order **AQE87** > **N117** > **AQE98**. Interestingly, according to Moukheiber et al. [32], the α -transition temperatures (of dry polymers) follow the order **AQE98** > **AQE87** > **N117**, with α -transition temperatures of both Aquivion membranes exceeding 120 °C, while Nafion's α -transition occurs just below 105 °C. At the same time, it was clearly shown by multiple authors that when the α -transition temperature is exceeded, the associated conformational changes allow pronounced water uptake [22, 31]. However, our results suggest that exceeding α -transition temperature is not a necessary condition for the onset of overswelling, contrary to earlier assumptions [19, 20]. Nevertheless, it should be highlighted that there is some ambiguity in the reported α -transition temperatures. The timescale of the presented experiments likely played a key role in the overswelling of the membranes – as shown in **Figure 1**, steady state is not reached even after 800 h, indicating continued water absorption. Therefore, one can assume that excessive swelling can occur even below the α -transition temperature if the polymer is exposed to liquid water for prolonged periods. It seems that excessive swelling is mainly driven by the polymer's hydrophilicity and the reduced matrix stiffness at elevated temperatures (which acts against water uptake). Fascinating results consistent with this suggestion were presented by Fumagalli et al. [39]. They showed that the Nafion 117 membrane did not reach equilibrium during swelling, even after six years of exposure to liquid water at 25 °C. They hypothesised that the osmotic pressure resulting from the absorbed water

creates mechanical stress inside the membrane, analogous to a creep test, and that the lack of steady state during swelling is connected to ongoing plastic deformation.

3.3 Internal structure analysis by SAXS and WAXS

To investigate the changes in the internal structure of membranes occurring during the hydrothermal treatment, the membrane samples were analysed by SAXS. The samples were measured in the as-received state, after the activation and after undergoing the hydrothermal treatment. The resulting 1D scattering curves of **N117** are shown in **Figure 33**, curves of other membranes are depicted in **Figure S5**. The SAXS profiles of all samples possess two distinct correlation peaks. The origins of these two peaks are still debated. At higher values of q , there is the “ionomer peak” it comes from either scattering on the hydrophilic domains [18] or on the hydrophobic polymer aggregates [39, 40]. At lower values there is the “matrix knee” connected to crystallinity of the polymer [18, 41]. As can be seen from **Figure 3**, the positions of both peaks shift towards lower q values with hydration which reflects the expansion of the internal structure.

Figure 3 – 1D SAXS diffractograms in the log-log scale for series of N117 membrane samples.

The scattering vector values (q -vectors) and corresponding evaluated d -spacing ($d = 2\pi q^{-1}$) are summarised in Error! Reference source not found.S1. The d -spacing for the ionomer peak and the matrix knee can be interpreted as the distances between the hydrophilic domains (alternatively hydrophobic polymer aggregates) and crystallites, respectively. The data from **Table S1** are visualised in **Figure 4**. In the as-received state, the membranes exhibit a compact internal structure, with no remarkable differences observed even between the individual membrane types. Upon activation, the internal structure expands, as indicated by increased d -spacing of both the matrix knee and the

ionomer peak. Again, differences between individual membrane types with exception of **F940** are negligible. In contrast, the structure expansion following the hydrothermal treatment is dramatically more pronounced.

Figure 4 – Quantitative parameters of the internal structure of tested samples evaluated from SAXS experiments in terms of distances between a) crystalline domains, b) ionomer domains and c), d) correlation of these distances with water content.

The correlation distances between structural domains correlate very well with water content in the membranes (**Figure 4c,d**) demonstrating that this expansion is driven/accompanied by water uptake. The linear relationship between water content and domain spacing in Nafion was well documented before [42-44]. Interestingly, our data show that this applies regardless of the membrane type and state which suggests similarity of the structural features and types of interactions between all investigated membranes and water. Hydrothermally treated **F940** seems to be the exception from this trend. In this case, the ionomer peak d -spacing does not fall into the established linear relationship, while the matrix knee d -spacing follows the expected behaviour reasonably well.

Another noteworthy feature in the data presented in **Figure 4c,d** is the difference in the slopes of the two d -spacing dependencies on water content. The matrix knee d -spacing increases nearly five times more steeply with rising water content compared to the ionomer peak d -spacing. This discrepancy in

slope may reflect a reduction in crystallinity during the hydrothermal treatment, as will be discussed later.

As already discussed above, the membranes exhibit significant differences in their affinity towards water. Among the extruded membranes, **AQE87** shows the highest, **N117** medium and **AQE98** lowest degree of water swelling after the hydrothermal treatment. This trend is also reflected in the expansion of their internal structure. As already mentioned, crystallinity of the membranes is expected to play an important role in the absorption of water. Therefore, to investigate the role of the crystalline structure, wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) was used to characterise the membranes, in their as-received and activated states, and after the hydrothermal treatment. **Figure S7** shows the WAXS diffractograms and their fits used to determine crystallinity with respect to the dry portion of the samples (excluding the contribution of water). As depicted in **Figure 5a**, in the as-received state, **N117** exhibits the highest degree of crystallinity, while **AQE87** is the least crystalline. This is somewhat surprising as based on the molecular structure, **AQE98** should be the most crystalline as it has the most PTFE units per $-SO_3H$ group. Moreover, this effect should be amplified by the short side chains that allow for more efficient packing of the backbone (in comparison with the long side chains in **N117**) [18]. However, same as many other properties of the PFSA membranes, the crystallinity is highly dependent on the history of the samples, including the manufacturing process, which can explain this discrepancy.

Figure 5 – a) crystallinity of membrane samples in as-received, activated and hydrothermally treated states, b) and the change of crystallinity relative to the as-received state. The percentages at the foot of the columns in a) indicate the portion of the WAXS diffractogram area belonging to the polymer matrix (remainder is water).

Upon activation, all membranes showed a reduction in crystallinity. The hydrothermal treatment led to a further decrease in crystallinity in **N117**, **F940** and **AQE87**. As shown in **Figure 5b**, **F940** exhibits the most pronounced decrease in crystallinity between the activated and treated states. Interestingly, despite the severe degradation observed in the treated **F940**, the material still displays a semicrystalline character – likely originating from the PTFE reinforcing mesh. The curious behaviour of **AQE98**, which exhibits an increase in crystallinity after the hydrothermal treatment, may stem from sample

heterogeneity or, potentially, from a measurement error, as the WAXS profiles are largely dominated by water signal (as will be shortly discussed below).

The crystallinity reduction following significant water uptake agrees with observations reported in literature [20, 42]. It is likely that the high water absorption during hydrothermal treatment was facilitated by the disruption of crystalline domains (and/or vice versa). This is supported by the inverse correlation between crystallinity and water uptake: after the treatment, the crystallinity of the hydrothermally treated samples decreases in the order **AQE98 > N117 > AQE87**, while the extent of water absorption follows exactly opposite trend.

It needs to be noted, that the WAXS results were impacted by the significant water content in most of the samples, which introduced errors in the crystallinity evaluation precision, as water signals dominated the data in most cases (**Figure S7**). The percentages at the foot of the columns in **Figure 5a** indicate the portion of WAXS diffractogram's area belonging to the polymer matrix – the lower the percentage, the lower the reliability of the crystallinity value. Also, all the obtained crystallinity values are higher than those reported in literature (10 – 15 %) [18, 32]. However, while the crystallinity values in the samples (especially those with high contents of water) are rather qualitative, the results clearly demonstrate that water absorption decreases crystallinity of membranes (and decreased crystallinity promotes further water absorption).

3.5 Water states investigation by DSC

As shown above, the increasing water content in PFSA membranes seems to be the main cause of the changes in their behaviour. Therefore, to obtain more insight into the properties of the water embedded in the membrane structure, the samples were further analysed by DSC. Sample **F940** was not further studied due to its significant deterioration during the hydrothermal treatment.

An example of DSC thermogram is depicted in **Figure S8**. It is a well-known fact that a certain part of the water molecules in PFSA membranes interacts strongly with the $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups (hydration shell formation) and consequently does not freeze [18, 45, 46]. Thus, the values of enthalpy associated with water freezing (and melting) obtained from the DSC experiments were used to calculate the amount of (non-)freezing water in the membrane samples. The calculations (**Eq. S1, S2**) were done assuming that the freezing water behaves like bulk water (i.e. their specific fusion and melting enthalpies of the freezing water in the membrane are equal to values for bulk water). Finally, by subtracting the amount of freezing water from the total water content in the samples, it is possible to obtain the amount of the water that does not freeze during the DSC scan (non-freezing water; **Eq. S3**).

The results are provided in **Figure 6**, which combines information about ratio of mass of water to mass of dry membrane together with the numbers of freezing ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}}$) and non-freezing ($\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}}$) water molecules per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. The $\lambda_{\text{freezing}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}}$ values in activated **N117** reached 5 and 21, respectively. In hydrothermally treated **N117**, $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 33$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 44$ were found. These values are in a reasonable agreement with data from literature. For example, in a “pre-boiled” **N117**, values of $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 8.3$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 12.4$ were found by Kalapos et al. [47], while $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 5.6$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 9.1$ were reported by Lue et al. [46]. Finally, Alberti et al. [22] immersed “pre-boiled pre-dried” **N117** membranes in liquid water contained in a small Teflon vessels; the vessels were then enclosed and heated to various temperatures. After 220 h of equilibration at 120 °C they received total λ (i.e. $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} + \lambda_{\text{non-freezing}}$) ≈ 36 , while total $\lambda \approx 71$, i.e. value closer to the hydrothermally treated samples obtained in our experiments, was reached after 200 h at 140 °C.

Figure 6 – H₂O content in the membrane samples before and after the thermal treatment, different colours indicate proportions of freezing and unfreezing water calculated from DSC data together with corresponding λ values. **A** and **T** denote “activated” and hydrothermally “treated” membrane, respectively. “Minimum” freezing water corresponds to the amount of water that was measured in samples that were dried at 25 °C in air (RH \approx 38%); such samples did not exhibit the freezing/melting peak in DSC.

Figure 6 reveals a clear distinction between the behaviour of Aquivion membranes and the **N117** membrane. In the case of Aquivions, most of the water introduced during the hydrothermal treatment is non-freezing, i.e. in contact with $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups, whereas in **N117**, the majority of the newly introduced water freezes. The large portion of non-freezing water in Aquivions points to lack of bulk-like water inside the membranes. This may be a consequence of small ionomer domains (large surface to volume ratio) due to which most of the water molecules are always in the vicinity of the $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups and thus cannot form the freezing bulk phase. Interesting results, relevant in this context, were obtained by Lin et al. [48] – an increase of non-freezing water content was correlated with a decrease of hydrophilic domain sizes in a pre-stretched Nafion 117. The smaller hydrophilic domains in Aquivions are likely due to their short side chains. However, morphological arrangement that would allow **AQE87** to have nearly no bulk-like water and at the same time the most expanded microstructure (**Figure 4**) is hard to imagine.

These differences in water accommodation inside the nanoscale morphology are possibly linked to the extent of changes in resistivity in the membranes discussed above (**Figure 1** and **Table 3**). According to Gebel [21], upon water uptake, two primary effects influence proton transport: dilution of the charge-transport groups and morphological reorganisation (i.e., domain development). At low to moderate hydration levels, increased water content enhances conductivity by promoting a favourable morphology for proton conduction (decrease of tortuosity). However, beyond a certain hydration threshold, further water uptake leads to conductivity loss due to charge dilution (the curve of dependence of conductivity on water content exhibits a maximum). At excessively high water contents, the membrane's behaviour resembles that of a colloidal dispersion.

In the context of the previous paragraph, our results suggest that the amount of water introduced inside **N117** during the hydrothermal treatment was not high enough to significantly disrupt its ionic conductivity. This is evidenced by the relatively small resistivity increase of 7 % in case of **N117** (**Table 3**). In contrast, in both **AQE98** and **AQE87** the resistivity increase was more pronounced with 68 % and 247 % change, respectively. This indicates that the (possibly) larger hydrophilic domains associated with longer side chains in **N117** (and the mesoscale domain arrangement connected with them) may offer greater stability against conductivity loss during excessive swelling.

Figure 7 illustrates the role of different water states in the observed changes by plotting change in λ ($\lambda_{\text{treated}} - \lambda_{\text{activated}}$) against change in domain spacing and resistivity. **Figure 7a** and **Figure 7b** show that the microstructural expansion described in connection to **Figure 4** correlates with the change in total water content. In contrast, the change in resistivity correlates more strongly with the change in amount of non-freezing water – lower levels of non-freezing water in the Aquivion membranes correspond to

increased resistivity (**Figure 7c**). The exact underlying cause of this correlation remains unclear. Furthermore, the lack of correlation between changes in domain spacing and resistivity (**Figure 7d**) suggests that charge transport decline is more influenced by how water is accommodated within the membrane than by structural expansion alone.

Figure 7 – Illustration of how changes in water states $\lambda_{treated} - \lambda_{activated}$ relate to changes in observed quantities, $X_{treated} - X_{activated}$, where X is: a) lamellar domain spacing, b) ionomer domain spacing and c) resistivity. d) Relationship between changes in resistivity and changes in domain spacing.

Nonetheless, it is important to note that the structural changes induced in **N117** (although they do not seem to impair intrinsic proton transport) still have negative consequences, such as reduced mechanical strength. In addition, the pronounced volume expansion may be problematic in practical applications, such as catalyst-coated membranes for PEM electrolyzers.

3.4 Surface morphology probing by AFM

Surface morphology of the membrane samples was examined using AFM. Selected images are provided in **Section S3** of the Supporting Information. The samples were observed in their as-received, activated, and hydrothermally treated states. The presence of water in the activated and treated membranes reduced the resolution of the adhesivity mapping. Moreover, analysis of the hydrothermally treated

samples was challenging due to their uneven surfaces and mechanical softness, which frequently led to probe-induced damage.

Both sides of the membranes were investigated at different resolutions. Overview scans (10 and 3 μm scan sizes) revealed distinct morphological differences between the two sides of each membrane, likely originating from the fabrication process. Images with a 1 μm scan size were used to identify suitable regions free of surface defects or contamination for detailed imaging. High-resolution scans (350 nm scan size) revealed a corrugated and inhomogeneous surface morphology. To emphasise fine structural details, selected topographical images were mathematically processed using an FFT analysis with stopband filter 55 nm.

AFM observations revealed two phase structure on the surface of samples. An example shown in **Figure 6** for the as-received **AQE98** membrane demonstrates strong correlation among the topography, adhesivity, and elastic modulus maps. A clear two-phase character is evident: areas with lower modulus (softer) also exhibit higher adhesivity (stickier). These softer features are more readily indented/pressed by the AFM probe and therefore appear as topographically depressed. Such regions are likely less reinforced by the polymer matrix and correspond to more swollen areas. This phenomenon can be observed on as-received samples **N117** and **AQE87** as well. Similarly, activated **N117** and **AQE98** samples show topography – modulus correlation.

As shown in **Figure 7** for the **N117**, the height difference between the depressed and elevated regions increases with the degree of swelling (from the as-received to the treated state).

The lateral sizes and distances of the soft, sunken features were visually quantified and subsequently statistically analysed, with results presented in **Figure 8**. No clear relationship between these parameters and the membrane type was observed. An increase of both parameters from the activated state to the treated state is observed for all membranes. However, expected minimum for as-received state was not confirmed. It must be recognised that the changes to the membrane surface caused by water exposure are complex and significant.

The AFM-derived dimensions were also compared with SAXS data in **Figure 9**. The sizes obtained from AFM show partial agreement with the matrix knee d -spacing, particularly in the as-received and activated states, whereas this correlation diminishes after hydrothermal treatment. No such agreement was found between the AFM sizes and the ionomer peak d -spacing.

These results indicate that the AFM observed surface features differ from the morphology of the bulk, which is an often-observed phenomenon in complex polymer systems.

Figure 6 – Example AFM scans of as-received **AQE98** showing the two-phased morphology of the surface; a) measured topography, b) FFT-filtered topography, c) adhesion, d) modulus

Figure 7 – FFT-filtered topography AFM scans of **N117** in different states; a) as-received – vertical scale 2.6 nm, b) activated – vertical scale 8.7 nm, c) treated – vertical scale 15.9 nm.

Figure 8 – Quantitative parameters extracted from FFT-filtered topographical AFM images; a) distance between the topographically sunken features, b) sizes of the topographically sunken features.

Figure 9 – Comparison of quantitative parameters obtained from AFM with d-spacing values from SAXS.

4 Conclusion

Four commercial membranes were subjected to an 800 h hydrothermal treatment in liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa, with membrane resistance continuously monitored. In addition to that, membranes were analysed by various methods including SAXS, WAXS and AFM. All treated membranes showed loss of ionic conductance and mechanical strength which can be attributed to observed morphological changes (crystallinity loss, volume expansion). Cast and reinforced **Fumapem F-940-RF** completely delaminated from its reinforcing mesh, indicating poor structural integrity, while extruded membranes (**Nafion 117**, **Aquivion E98-05S**, and **Aquivion E87-05S**) degraded less severely but still significantly.

Three key findings were identified in this study. First, the extent of performance degradation was not correlated with the α -transition temperature, contrary to expectations. Second, the degree of degradation associated with overswelling was primarily determined by the membrane's hydrophilicity (i.e. its equivalent weight). Third, the polymer side-chain length influenced the water accommodation within the membrane's internal domains. Shorter side chains likely result in more tortuous ion-

conducting pathways and smaller water domains. The latter was indicated by DSC measurements, which showed a nearly negligible amount of bulk-like (freezing) water in membranes with the short-side chains.

The continuous decline in ionic conductivity indicated that water uptake in all membranes did not reach equilibrium even after 800 h of hydrothermal treatment. In PEM electrolyzers operated at elevated temperature and pressure, such persistent hydration (leading to overswelling) would likely cause ongoing membrane degradation and increase hydrogen permeability. These effects warrant further investigation.

5 Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process.

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the grammar and readability of the text. The authors subsequently reviewed and edited all content as necessary and take full responsibility for the final version of the manuscript.

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